

Higher Education performance of Muslim Countries Islamic Economics as an Illustrative Case

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The purpose of this paper is (i) to state the objectives of higher education commensurate with Islamic requirements; (ii) to examine the current state of higher education performance in Muslim majority countries with a view to identifying the main issues it faces using Islamic economics as illustration and (iii) to present in outline a program for improvement. The constraints of time and resources do not permit us to present an all covering discussion on the subject. Instead of dealing with specifics, we shall focus on directional and attitudinal issues of substance. We are aware of the limitations of the exercise but find it rewarding.

Keywords: Objectives of education; Islamic economics and Issues in higher learning; remedial action.

1. Introduction

Professor Abdul Hamid A. Abu Sulayman in his petite work on higher education in the Muslim world considers inadequacy of performance in the area expressive of the *umma's* backwardness in all aspects of life (2014. 2). This short paper presents an empirical exploration of this inadequacy using Islamic economics as an illustrative case.

The view of education in Islam is based on verses of the Quran and the Prophetic *traditions* that exhort the believers for learning, emphasizing the benefits that flow from the acquisition of knowledge. Indeed, no religion save Islam has given so much importance to learning; the very opening verses of the revelation instruct humans to 'read'. The Qur'an makes humans' ability to read and write for educating self as their definitional characteristic distinctive of other creation. Humans were

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equipped to take charge of the planet with all its resources intended to promote creativity and growth for transforming self from lower to higher stages of evolution – for becoming ‘*insaan*’ from mere ‘*being*’² Virtue and vice both remained mingled in humans as they were granted freedom to choose either course as guide to action on earth, Education was expected to keep them on the path of virtue but discretion granted could promote the opposite attributes as well. Thus, education could and did lead to both construction and destruction over the course of history. The divine wisdom consisted of a system of reward for good deeds and punishment for the wicked here and in the hereafter. Thus, moral aspects were intrinsic to Islamic systems of education.

The real journey on the education path begins after basic learning of language and numbers and their elementary use to have a feel of the happenings around and the basic human problems.² Learning grows into education after schooling. Colleges, universities and professional institutions are the cradles’ of higher education, research and exploration. This paper aims to have a look at the state of higher education in the Muslim world. It is a vast and difficult terrain for the confines of a paper in terms of time, space and resources. We must define the boundaries, limitations and utility of our exercise.

1.1 The design

To begin with, we use Islamic economics including finance as an illustrative case in the Muslim world on a selective basis from 1975 onwards when the subject had just emerged as a formal academic discipline. The progress of the subject in higher education over the past four plus decades has been laudable, especially in the financial sector. There are gaps misdirection too. But new disciplines do face teething problems. Even mainstream economics is not yet a body of settled conclusions readily applicable to policy. Theoretical formulations can rarely be conclusive in a dynamic social order as of today. Change makes existing problems complicated and new ones continue cropping up.

² Education is what is left in you beyond the classroom lessons; what sort of person it makes you. “Real education is something one take up, not as a means to make a living, but as a habit of being through a lifetime.”

Schooling is the bedrock on which the edifice of higher education is raised. The content and quality of learning at that level has serious limitations in the Muslim world to link it up with college education. However, we cannot discuss them here. Instead we take the risk of closing our eyes to the schooling limitations for the discussion that follows. Admittedly, such an exploration of the higher education terrain would detract from the utility of our discussion on higher education in the Muslim world but we do hope to illuminate some of its darker corners.

Structure of the paper

The Section of the paper following introduction deals with the broad overall objectives of education from Islamic perspective. Next, we state and analyze some basic issues relating to higher education in the Muslim countries in the field of economics providing broader generalizations where relevant. This would necessitate spelling out some policy measures to improve the situation. Finally, we close the discussion with a few concluding observations.

2. Objectives of higher education

We have no consensus on what the objectives of education in general are or should be in Islam, there is even less on the aims of higher education. The reason is that educational aims - irrespective of level - do not exist or can be conceived of in vacuum. A social milieu has to be their frame of reference. Thus, aims of education cannot be thought of independent of factors – historical, customary, juristic, economic and political - affecting the social dynamics over time and space. We have discussed the issues concerning the structural designs, curricula and reading material contextual to higher education in economics thread bare already in a recent paper (Hasan 2008). We need not go over the argument again as things have since shown not much change. What has remained typically frozen is the juridical attitude towards higher education.

2.1 Colonial hangover

When Qur'an opened with an exhortation to read and informed us that Allah was the first teacher of the humans – men and women – the reference was to their innate faculty to learn and gain knowledge as

distinct from other creations. Ability to learn was the necessary condition for educating self. For, education is a liberating force giving us a feel of freedom; breathing of fresh air. Education in Islamic economics, the illustrative material of our work, is no different.

2 This implies the avoidance of the role of mosque in imparting educational instructions even as much classical uristic explorations owe their origin to work at mosque attached libraries. Even today the grand mosque at the centre of the International Islamic University of Malaysia (IIUM) and its sprawling library stand face to face in that rendition. learning if you like - takes us out of our childhood. It helps us break our mental shackles, Pursuit of knowledge for its own sake is pleasurable but universities, at times, promote Ivory Tower thinking. We believe that the pleasure of kite flying is informative of the wind speed and direction but education and research must serve substantive ends, especially in resource deficient developing economies. Unwittingly, bulk of the work coming out of higher education institutions in the Muslim world in the field of economics as in others is grossly inadequate in quantum and quality. There is either a timorous submission to historical “pull back or to Western ideas and prescriptions. There is little realization that education planning must not be premised on alien blue prints however cozy they might look It must conform to Islamic ends It must erect a system invoking an urge to learn and research in students - the final product. On delivery must rest the judgments regarding academic performance of the institutions and their funding. The cost-benefit analysis is a must. The notion of excellence is, or must be, coextensive with such analysis. We shall show that neither the ‘pull back’ obsession nor the ‘modernity elation’ meet Muslim requirements. Higher education is imparted in colleges, universities and specialized institutions. For this paper, we have focused on institutions where Islamic economics and finance are major areas of instructions.

Let us first take a look at the historical ‘pull back’ and reform its impact prescribes for Islamic economics education. We do not document our argument unless challenged as we do not want to create divisions among the learned. However, those who *are in touch with the literature on Islamic economics would readily agree* that we have a group of influential writers that is vocal about Islamic economics not freeing itself of Western frameworks and going back to its classical juridical roots. For that, they insist on creating first a *performing* Muslim society through

dawahh (preaching). Until an ideal social order is created, they take recourse in highlighting the weaknesses of the mainstream economics blaming on it all the ills modern economies suffer from. They reject scarcity of resources, pursuit of self-interest and maximizing behavior as Western afflictions non-amiable to moral reforms for accommodation in Islamic economics. A close look at the bibliography of writings critical of these mainstream concepts reveals that most of the argument is borrowed from mainstream itself; there are not many references of Islamic origin. When these and similar ideas are modified and defended as useful for Islamic economics, they do not comment or dispute. Rather, there is a candid tendency in the literature to shun critical evaluations unmindful of the fact that such evaluations are needed for the progress of the discipline. Why this is so?

History tells us that Muslim conquest of the world had peaked within three to four hundred years of its advent on the scene; they had downed both the mighty Roman and Iranian empires. During the same time Muslims had emerged as the knowledge leaders of the world – in philosophy, astrology, mathematics, medicine, jurisprudence, sociology, navigation and others. After these glorious years Muslims were mostly fighting among themselves for the chunks of land until after the close of the First World War Europe dismembered their (Ottoman) empire into colonized small bits. That in-fight among Muslims continues even after the dawn of independence from slavery. Muslims have killed more Muslims than have non-Muslims after the Second World War. Arrogance and corruption dominate Muslim lands with some exceptions. From needles to airplanes including prayer related materials are imported from abroad. What has been the Muslim contribution to the growing stock of knowledge over the recent centuries?

2.2 Universities: some issues

Universities are the seats of higher learning and research. The range and quality of their activities depends on how these institutions are run and in what sort of socio-political environs they operate. Initially universities started as public sector entities; most of them were established in developing countries by the legislative action – central or state – during the colonial era but mostly after independence. It was in the second half of the preceding century that private sector universities, colleges and other institutions of higher learning started proliferating in a noticeable

way for several reasons. Finance was a major one but soon the rising wave of liberalization – political and economic – tended to be increasingly significant.

Whether public or private, a typical university is supposed to carry the mark of *excellence* with its name. How one defines this excellence and how it is, or must be, measured is a moot point. There is much controversy on the criteria and the resultant annual ranking of the institution of higher learning worldwide, wherein institutions in lower income economies lag far behind.³ The result is that many developing countries seem to have an attitude of indifference toward these rankings.³ Some as India have developed a parallel criteria set for internal ranking. Be it as it is, the relevance of a notion of excellence can hardly be denied;⁴ it is needed at least for cost-benefit analyses and funding decisions.

Figure1: Rising trend of public expenditure on education in the world

Source: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SE.XPD.TOTL.GD.ZS> (Trend added)

3 The charge in developing world is that such rankings smack of bias. Its validity apart, it is true that the criteria of evaluation are based on what is largely relevant for the Western educational institutions and foreign to away in the developing world. To me, it looks akin to the case of fox inviting the crane for supper, using flat plates, and then blaming the crane of being poor at eating.

4 But many are also to ignore. India is a case in point. Upset at poor showing of Indian institutions in the rankings year after year, the Central government has decided to boast financially and otherwise some 10 institutions to see them among the top 100 at the earliest.

Presumably, OIC through its Statistics Office at Istanbul may take up the work of developing excellence norms and of ranking the institutions in the Muslim world.

Expenditure on education as a percent of World GDP has been rising over the years running over 4.4% after 2008 and touching 4.8% in 2014 as Figure 1 shows. There is presumption that the larger part of this rise has gone to boost higher education. What is the position in Muslim countries?

3. Higher Education in Muslim lands

Let us follow the criterion on which the Figure 1 is based and see what proportion of GDP in various Muslim countries is spent on education but one must clearly understand that parents and private institutions spent substantial amount of money on education, especially on quality improvement, which the public expenditure criterion ignores. Also, per head expenditure is a better criterion than the GDP proportion especially for comparisons over time and space. In Figure 2 the ratios are picked up from the Human Development Reports of the UNDP. These reports do not have data for all countries nor is the division of expenditures for different categories of education available. Despite limitations, the situation summary presented reveals some interesting facts about education in Muslim countries.

It is worth noting that the expenditure to GDP ratio for Muslim countries is on a higher side even in some poorer African countries. There are countries where it is greater than the average for developed economies. In the majority of cases the ratio is higher than the medium income category. Overall, the community is spending generously on education; the religious instructions are being followed. Why the record of Muslims to the fast-growing stock of knowledge is then so pathetically poor both in quantity and quality? Let us illustrate.

Figure: Public expenditure on education as ratio of GDP in Muslim countries in 2012

The contributions of Muslim scholars dominate areas in religion, arts and humanities; it is rare in physical sciences and technology. In social sciences, Islamic economics and finance lead the pack. Here too publications drawing attention of the world are countable. Journals attracting world attention are fewer. Readership in either case is meager. An objective test is the appearance of working papers and articles on the RePEc Archive. I do not have resources enough to conduct research on various aspects that it provides data on; still a small effort has been made. Not more than four academic journals dealing exclusively with Islamic economics and finance are registered with the archive.

We took the list of OIC member countries and opened the top 25 authors list for October 2018 for listed countries. We recorded the count of Muslim and non-Muslim contributors in each case. The downloads and views for the top Muslim scholar in each country were recorded. Findings are briefly reported as under:

Table 1: Data Availability status at RePEc 2018 (OIC Countries)

Available for 30	Not Available for 27
Albania, Algeria, Azerbaijan, Bahrain,	Afghanistan, Benin, Cameroon, Chad,
Bangladesh, Brunei, Burkina Faso	Comoros, Côte D'Ivoire, Djibouti, Gabon,
Egypt,	Gambia, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Guyana,
Indonesia, Iran, Jordan, Kazakhstan,	Iraq, Kirgiz Republic, Libya, Maldives,
Kuwait, Lebanon, Malaysia, Morocco,	Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Sierra Leone,
Mozambique, Nigeria Oman, Palestine,	Somalia, Suriname, Syria, Togo,
Pakistan, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Senegal,	Turkmenistan, Yemen.
Sudan, Tunisia, Turkey, Uganda, UAE,	

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It is regrettable that almost half of the Muslim countries have no or insignificant presence on the archive. Of the remaining 30 countries that appear there, the data for top five is provided in Table 2. The 18.4% of the contributors in these countries are non-Muslims; interestingly their ratio in Malaysia is 56%! The average long-run contribution of the top Muslim contributors at $440458/5 = 88091$ is not impressive.

It is interesting to note that there is no significant co-variation between the per capita national GDP level and RePEc performance. The above quantitative analysis of Muslim contribution to Islamic economics may not be free of blemishes but it does unmistakably reveal the academia contribution to knowledge falls much short of being redeemably commensurate with the generous public funding of education in the Muslim world. The academic system is not cost effective; per unit cost of deliverables is too high. The causes of this adverse cost-benefit scenario call for investigation of the causes.

Table2: Top five countries' performance

#	Country	Number of authors		Number		Total D + V
		Muslims	Others	Downloads	Views	
1	Pakistan	25	0	11026	48899	59925
2	Turkey	23	2	28974	216561	245535
3	Bangladesh	22	3	10057	31130	41187
4	Lebanon	21	4	8167	62998	71 16 5
5	Malaysia	11	14	11328	29229	40757
Total Authors		112	23	69552	388817	458369

Note: Data derived from RePEc. Countries arranged as per Muslim authors number

For 12 countries⁷ we had values for expenditure-on-education-ratios and their ranks as per RePEc contribution. The sample is adequate from a population of thirty countries for which data is available. We ran simple OLS regression taking as independent variable Y and expenditure ratio as X. The result is as follows:

$$Y = 0.26 + 1.46X - 0.086 \text{ (The coefficient is significant at 5\%)}$$

It follows that in general increase in expenditure on education has led to an increase in contribution to knowledge in Muslim countries even as the result is not elating; an expenditure increase in as much as 1.46% of GDP raises rank by just one unit. Thus, it is too costly an affair relative to the benefit.

The picture of Higher education that emerges from the foregoing analysis is bleak to put it straight. The crux of the problem is that benefits are low in comparison of generous communal expenditure on education.

More than half the Muslim population across countries fails to find its way to prosperity in the darkness of ignorance. More than that, those who are fortunate to reach college education are not getting education of the sort needed in economics and finance, our sample field. Where have we missed the bus? What follows may not sound sweet but a wakeup call is the need of the hour.

3.1 Some Comments

To begin with, many of the faculty in higher education institutions is far beyond their peak productive years. They can no longer dish out, save in exceptions, bright new ideas any longer. They grow to become lotus eaters and mark time to get promotions just by aging. Such faculty is thought-poor unable to provide quality supervision for research work. They believe in making the student struggle rudderless in pursuit of learning. For what is then, one wonders, the supervisor needed and hours are credited to his service record?

Their academic output of the faculty is meager and research stale as the above analysis shows. They are blocking the way of the young. One way is to lengthen students' years of study in frustration. I have seen many such whiteheads around in the Muslim world where I spent quarter of a century of my professional career. Political patronage fed on connection,

if not corruption, feeds the placement process unabated. Teachers were found claiming expertise in fields that they never studied or contributed to just for adding the tag of being a research guide to enrich their profile for promotion. They only tended to ruin the career of their charge. Research under such circumstance is perilous. Interestingly those who come out of the process successfully choose to perpetuate the process as though in revenge.

Another serious research issue concerning Islamic economics and finance is the imitative tilt towards using mathematics and econometric modeling in dissertation writing. We have already discussed the ill consequences of this tilt in a recent article on *Academic Sociology* (Hasan 2018) and need not repeat the argument here save reiterating that the overemphasis on using these tools, more presumably in Malaysia, is killing innovative urges in young minds without much benefit to either academics or the profession. This perilous tilt needs urgent correction.

Grade inflation: The professional non-performance of the faculty is reflected not only in the low number and quality of their publications but in what may be described as ‘grade inflation’. In many universities of the Muslim world there is a system of students evaluating their teachers as in the West. After each semester students in each course fill forms to complete what is termed as ‘teachers -evaluation-ratting, the TER. In fact, TER strikes terror among the teachers and, in my opinion based on observation, does more harm than good to the cause of education. It breeds a system wherein the teacher has his, so to say, his hand at the throat of the student – he grades his performance in assignments tests and examinations – and the student in turn has his on the teacher’s at the end of semester; the TER exercise affecting his reputation and carrier. In this scenario each party seems saying to the other – “should you press, I shall also”. Eventually, both decide to oblige each other. The result is *grades inflation*. I have found cases of all students getting A grade with some teachers and a high degree of correlation between teachers’ TER sores and their students’ average grades!

Finally, there is the issue of publishing avenues. Even as Islamic economics and finance has now been on the scene for half a century or so, there is an agonizing dearth of good academic journals with wide circulation – there are not more than five or six in the area, even as the Muslims constitute the second largest religious group in the world. These

few journals too are not receiving adequate numbers of publishable articles.

9 Conferences are held too often and are well -attended. The journals divide conference papers among themselves for publication to overcome the paucity of regular contributions. Good comprehensive works, especially textbooks - are not many over time and space. Experience teaches that it is more rewarding to be a book seller than a book writer.

Concluding remarks

This small paper is a preliminary effort to look into a basic issue of delivery and its cost in higher education in the Muslim world. For that it selected the state of affairs in economics and finance as a reference point and the data on RePEc archive as a performance measure. It must be at once conceded that this approach may have more blemishes than the critics may dig out. Thus, no tall claims for this humble effort, but it does bring to light a few interesting facts about education in the Muslim world.

Public expenditure on education higher education is not lacking. The average of its ratio to GDP 20 countries in Figure 2 is quite high at 4.15% our study shows alarming performance inadequacy in higher education. Presumably, more money is being spent on having world class infra structural facilities – buildings, furniture and libraries than producing motivated teachers; a delivering academic environ is largely missing. Higher perks alone cannot make lotus eaters work. Psychology plays the part.

It tells us that the religion's special concern about education and emphasis on it as the key to world treasure and salvation in the hereafter must find pronounced expression in the practical affairs of the community; Muslim countries in general are spending more education than most developing countries but performance is not commensurate with money spent. It is an issue of academic sociology, not of economics. Possibly, drastic systemic overhaul could be the answer?

Finally, this humble effort must be judged on what it achieves not on what it lacks.

At least it opens a new and vital topic for research.

References

Abdul Hamid A. Abu Sulayman (2014): Revitalizing Higher education in the Muslim world, Occasional paper series 12, Pp. 1 -49, International Institute of Islamic Thought, Washington

Fatkullina, F. & Murozkina E. (2018): Modern higher education: problems and perspectives, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042815061170#!>

Hasan, Zubair, 2008. "Islamic Finance Education At The Graduate Level Current State And Challenges," *Islamic Economic Studies*, The Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI), vol. 16, pages 1-29.

Hasan, Zubair (2018): Academic sociology – predatory publishing and its consequences for Islamic economics and finance, *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, Kuala Lumpur, volume 10, Issue 1 (Emerald) PP. 6-19

Hasan, Zubair (2008): Islamic finance education at the graduate level: Current state and challenges, *Islamic Economic Studies, The Islamic Research and Training Institute (IRTI)*, vol. 16, pages 1-29.

RePEc Archive (November 30 2018): Top Authors Country Statistics

Smith, Christian (January, 2018): Higher education is drowning and its mortality corrosive to society. <file:///C:/Users/ZUBAIR%20HASAN/Desktop/New%20folder/Higher%20Education%20Is%20Drowning%20in%20BS%20-%20The%20Chronicle%20o>